

Determination of concentration of some selected physicochemical parameters of groundwater obtained from some selected boreholes in Jalingo metropolis, Taraba State

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Abstract

This study assessed the concentrations of selected physicochemical parameters in groundwater obtained from boreholes located in Jalingo Metropolis, Taraba State, using the Water Quality Index (WQI) approach. The WQI technique integrates multiple water quality parameters into a single, easily interpretable value for both scientific and non-scientific audiences. Twelve key physicochemical parameters were analyzed: pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), salinity, total chlorine, fluoride, chloride, total copper, total zinc, total cadmium, total iron, and hexavalent chromium (Cr⁶⁺). Water samples were collected from two boreholes situated in the Investment Quarters and Sabon Gari areas using a composite sampling technique. Comparison of the analyzed parameters with World Health Organization (WHO) standards revealed that all parameters were within acceptable limits except fluoride and cadmium, which exceeded recommended thresholds in samples from Investment Quarters. The computed WQI values were 93.47 for Investment Quarters and 2.69 for Sabon Gari, indicating that the water from Investment Quarters falls under the 'very poor' quality category, while water from Sabon Gari falls under the 'excellent' category. Consequently, groundwater from the Sabon Gari borehole is suitable for human consumption and domestic use, whereas the water from the Investment Quarters borehole is unfit for consumption.

Keywords: Water, borehole, physical parameters, Taraba State

1.0 Introduction

Water is one of the most abundant substances in nature. It is regarded as a vital necessity of life and is a part of every living cell [1]. Water is perhaps the most important nutrient in human diets. In fact, adults need to drink approximately 2 liters (8 glasses) of water every day to replenish the water that is lost from the body through the skin, respiratory tract, and urine [2]. Water covers about 70% of Earth's surface, makes up about 70% of body mass [2]. Water is the only substance that exists naturally on earth in all three physical states of matter - gas, liquid, and solid and it is always on the move among them [3]. The Earth has oceans of

liquid water and Polar regions covered by solid water. Energy from the sun is absorbed by liquid water in oceans, lakes, and rivers and gains enough energy for some of it to evaporate and enter the atmosphere as an invisible gas and water vapour. As the water vapour rises in the atmosphere it cools and condenses into tiny liquid droplets that scatter light and become visible as clouds. Under the proper conditions, these droplets further combine and become heavy enough to precipitate (fall out) as drops of liquid or if the air is cold enough, flakes of solid, thus returning to the surface of the Earth to continue this cycle of water between its uncondensed and vapor phases [2]. Pure water is colorless, odorless, and tasteless and so common

that you probably never think about how unique it is and how essential to life. Most plants and animals contain more than 60% water by volume. Without water, life would not have evolved on Earth, and it is the presence of water on Mars and some moons of Jupiter and Saturn that causes us to speculate about past or present life there as well [3]. Federal Government policy on water supply guarantees the provision of water as one of the primary needs of man. Water is used for different purposes including domestic and municipal supply, industrial water supply, food and beverage industries, aquatic life, boiler and water pharmaceutical, antibiotic requirement, transportation and process, recreation, and agricultural water supply [4]. Pollution of water affects drinking water, lakes, river and oceans all over the world. In most of the developing countries the major cause of death is consumption of polluted water. Water pollution affects all living species and also populations and the complete functioning of the ecosystem that lives in the water [5]. Interest in water analysis is due to the enormous importance of water to all categories of living things. Developing countries are witnessing changes in ground water which constitute another sources of potable water[6]. The purpose of this research work is to analyze the various water supply from boreholes in Sabongari and Investment quarters areas of Jalingo town in order to ascertain their extent of contaminations by human activities since it is one of the major sources of water for the peoples in the area, for their domestic activities. This is vital as there has not been any record on this aspect of research in the area. To achieve this, some physical and chemical parameters of water are assessed. The various sources of water may contain varying substances as suspension which may contaminate or be of economic benefit to the area. The sources of contamination of the water vary from domestic, agriculture, and natural sources. For instance, the indiscriminate disposal of refuse, animal dung, faeces and waste products from processing of rice and other cereals into streams. The natural sources involve the leaching of mineral resources found in the area [7]. The borehole water is sometimes commercialized to the entire neighborhood without treatment. Water tankers use some of this water as

their source of water, which they pump into their tanker vehicles with the help of low lift pumps. This is then taken to the town and sold to people without any treatment to make it potable. It is believed that when human eat or drink affects our health and wellbeing as diseases such as river blindness, cholera, typhoid, guinea worm, skin diseases, etc. all stem from drinking contaminated water. Therefore, it is paramount that an investigation such as this be carried out in order to inform the people of this area about the effects of drinking water that has not been made fit for drinking [8].

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Jalingo Metropolis lies between latitudes $8^{\circ} 47'$ to $9^{\circ} 01'N$ and longitudes $11^{\circ} 09'$ to $11^{\circ} 30'E$. It has boundary with Lau Local Government Area in the North, Yorro Local Government Area in the East and Ardo Kola Local Government Area in the South and West. The total land area of Jalingo is approximately 195km^2 . Jalingo Metropolis has a population of 139,845 people according to the 2006 population census, with a projected growth rate of 3%. Jalingo town lies on gently sloping land that leads to the great Muri plains and between 305m to 610m above sea level [9]. The ground level rises to a peak of about 914 meters above sea level in the south-east (ureau for Land and Survey, Taraba State Nigeria, 2000).

2.2 Sample Collection

Samples were generally collected by first washing the sample bottles with $0.5M \text{HNO}_3$ (trioxonitrate (v) acid) and rinsed with distilled water severally. The samples from the boreholes were collected by composite sampling technique. This was done by lowering the sampling bottle with a rope knotted at the neck of the bottle to ensure that the sample collected was not from the surface at locations where anthropogenic activities were carried out [10].

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria, Taraba State, and Jalingo town showing the sampling locations [5].

2.3 Physical Parameters Analysis of Water Sample

2.3.1 Determination Electrical Conductivity (μScm^{-1})

Electrical conductivity of the water samples was measured with the conductivity and salinity meter. The probe of the meter was inserted into the water sample and the central control switched to the conductivity position. A steady reading was recorded as the conductivity of the water in μScm^{-1} .

2.3.2 Determination of Total Dissolved Solids

Exactly 300 mL of water sample was filtered using Whatman filter paper. A clean evaporating dish was heated in a drying oven at 105°C for about 30 minutes and then cooled in desiccators for 10 minutes. The dish was weighed on a digital weighing balance. 100 mL of filtrate was poured into the evaporating dish and heated on a hot plate to dryness after which it was transferred to an oven for drying at 105°C for one hour. The dish was then allowed to cool briefly in air after which it was placed in desiccators to complete the cooling in a dry atmosphere and then weighed with content. In each case, the analysis was carried out in replicate (twice) for each sample [11].

Calculation:

$$\text{TDS (mg/L)} = \frac{(B - A) \times 100}{\text{mL of Sample}}$$

Where;

A = weight of dish alone

B = weight of residue and evaporating dish

2.3.3 Determination of Salinity (Extecth)

The conductivity meter has a salinity position so that as the probe is dipped into the water sample, the central switch is turned to the salinity position and when a steady reading is obtained, it is recorded as the salinity of the water sample in mg/L [12].

2.4 Chemical Analysis

2.4.1 Determination of pH (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

The pH meter was used for the determination of the pH of the water samples. Before the measurements, the pH meter was standardized with two buffer solutions of different pH values, namely; pH 4 and 9. The electrode was thoroughly rinsed and then dipped into the water samples until a steady pH is recorded as the pH of the water sample [13].

2.4.2 Procedure

Exactly 0.5 mL phosphate buffer was placed in a flask and 0.5 mL N,N-diethyl-p-phenylenediamine (DPD) reagent was added and approximately 0.1 g KI was added to that. 10 mL of samples was added and let to stand for 2 minutes. The solution was inserted into the spectrophotometer and read at 515 nm, the absorbance of two readings for each sample was recorded [13].

2.4.3 Determination of Fluoride

Fluoride was determined using SPANDS method. Standard concentrations of fluoride are prepared in the range of 0.1-10.0 mg F/L by diluting appropriate quantities of the standard fluoride solution to 50 mL with deionized water. 5 mL each of SPANDS solution and Zirconyl-acid reagent is pipetted and added to the standards and mixed well. The absorbance of the mixed solution is obtained using the spectrophotometer. A graph of the milligram F⁻ absorbance relationship was then plotted. A 50 mL of the sample to be measured was then taken and a 5 mL each of SPANDS solution and Zirconyl-acid reagent were added. The solution was mixed well and the absorbance was read.

2.4.4 Determination of Chloride

Chloride was measured by titration method. 50 mL of sample in a conical flask was taken. 2 mL of Potassium chromate was added to the sample solution. It was titrated against 0.02M silver nitrate until a persistent brick red color appeared which was the end point of the titration. A blank by placing 50 mL of chloride free distilled sample water was also conducted.

Calculation:

$$\text{Chloride (mg/L)} = \frac{(a-b) \times M \times 35.5 \times 1000}{V} \quad (1)$$

Where;

a = Volume of titrant (silver nitrate) for sample

b = Volume of titrant (silver nitrate) for blank

V = Volume of the sample in mL

M = Molarity of silver nitrate

2.4.5 Determination of Trace Metals

The trace metal analysis of total Co, total Zn, total Cd, total Fe, and Cr concentrations were determined using multiple water parameters colorimeter.

Concentrations of each trace metals in the water samples was determined after appropriate digestion of the samples using a COD reactor (digester). Prior to the digestion, for each trace metals and also the blank, 10 mL of the samples was collected into 18-mL colorimetric tubes and the reagents were added and then digested [14]

The digestion time for the trace metals varies, where some are digested for 30 minutes and others for 5 minutes. Only Zn was not digested since it does not need to be digested. The digested samples were then allowed to cooled and then transferred into the cuvette for the analysis. Average values of two replicates were taken for each sample determination. The average concentration value of the sample was considered for the analysis [15]. Prior to the beginning the experiment, the colorimeter was calibrated. It was accomplished by employing standard solutions of the known solute concentration to be calculated. The cuvettes were filled with standard solutions and set in the colorimeter's cuvette holder. A light ray of a specific wavelength, specific to the sample was directed toward the solution. The light passes through a number of filters and lenses. The lens aids in the correct navigation of the light beam. The filters divide the incoming light into distinct wavelengths, allowing just the needed wavelength to reach the test solution in the cuvette. The light beam was transmitted, reflected, and absorbed by the solution as it enters the cuvette. The transmitted ray strikes the photo-detector device, which measures the intensity of the transmitted light. The galvanometer reads the detector's electrical signals and displays them in digital form and thus, the reading were note down as the concentration of the heavy metals [16].

2.4.6 Calculation of Water Quality Index

$$Q_i = \left(\frac{V_n - V_o}{S_i - V_i} \right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where, V_n is estimated concentration of i parameter in the analyzed water

V_o is the ideal value of n parameter in pure water. This value is always zero for all physico-chemical parameters except pH with value of 7.0.

S_i is recommended value of n parameter.

The unit weight (W_i) for each physico-chemical parameter was calculated using the following equation (3).

$$W_i = \frac{K}{S_i} \quad (3)$$

Where,

K is a proportionality constant. The value of K can be calculated using equation (4).

$$K = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{S_i}\right)} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the overall WQI was calculated using the following expression:

$$WQI = \frac{\sum Q_i W_i}{\sum W_i}$$

3.0 Result and Discussion

Some marked variations in the physical and chemical parameters were observed between two study area (Investment Quarters and Sabon Gari). The results are presented in Table 1 to 4.

Table 1: Physicochemical Parameters of water samples obtained from boreholes in Investment Quarters and Sabon Gari in Jalingo Metropolis, Taraba State [14].

S/N	Parameter	Investment Quarters 1 st reading	Investment Quarters 2 nd reading	Mean ± SD	Sabon Gari 1 st reading	Sabon Gari 2 nd reading	Mean ± SD	Standard (WHO)
1.	pH	7.76	7.64	7.70±0.09	6.64	6.64	6.64±0.00	6.5 – 8.5
2.	Conductivity (µS/cm)	560.00	560.00	560.00±0.00	160.00	160.00	160.00±0.00	1000
3.	Total dissolved solids (mg/L)	448.00	448.00	448.00±0.00	128.00	128.00	128.00±0.00	500
4.	Salinity/mg/L	308.00	308.00	308.00±0.00	88.00	88.00	88.00±0.00	500
5.	Total chlorine (mg/L)	0.10	0.10	0.10±0.00	0.08	0.08	0.08±0.00	4
6.	Fluoride (mg/L)	0.53	0.53	0.53±0.00	0.00	0.01	0.005±0.007	0.05
7.	Chloride (mg/L)	170.48	170.48	170.8±0.00	48.70	48.70	48.70±0.00	250
8.	Total Copper (mg/L)	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01±0.00	1.3
9.	Total Zinc (mg/L)	0.01	0.03	0.025±0.007	0.02	0.02	0.02±0.00	3
10.	Total Cadmium (mg/L)	0.00	0.01	0.005±0.007	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00	0.005
11.	Total Iron (mg/L)	0.02	0.01	0.015±0.007	0.00	0.00	0.00±0.00	2
12.	Hexavalent Chromium (mg/L)	0.02	0.02	0.02±0.00	0.02	0.03	0.025±0.007	0.05

Table 2: Results of the Physico-chemical Parameters Analysis and Calculation of the Water Quality Index for InvestmentQuarters[14].

S/N	Parameter	Standard (Sn)	1/Sn	Sum. 1/Sn	$K = 1/\text{sum.Sn}$	$W_n = K/S_n$	Ideal value	$V_n = \text{Mean conc.}$	V_n/S_n	$Q_n = V_n/S_n * 100$	$W_n Q_n$
1	PH	8.5	0.118	449.49	0.002	0.0002	7	7.7	0.91	90.59	0.02
2	Conductivity	1000	0.01	449.49	0.002	2.22	0	560	0.56	56.00	0.0001
3	TDS	500	0.02	449.49	0.002	4.45	0	448	0.89	89.60	0.0003
4	Salinity	500	0.02	449.49	0.002	4.45	0	308	0.62	61.60	0.0002
5	Total chlorine	500	0.002	449.49	0.002	4.45	0	0.1	0.002	0.02	8.89
6	Fluorine	0.05	20	449.49	0.002	0.45	0	0.53	10.60	1060	47.16
7	Chloride	250	0.04	449.49	0.002	8.89	0	170.8	0.68	68.32	0.0006
8	Copper	1.3	0.77	449.49	0.002	0.001	0	0	0.00	0.0	0.0
9	Zinc	3	0.33	449.49	0.002	0.007	0	0.025	0.008	0.83	0.0006
10	Cadmium	0.05	200	449.49	0.002	0.45	0	0.005	1.0	100	44.49
11	Iron	2	0.5	449.49	0.002	0.001	0	0.015	0.0075	0.75	0.08
12	Cr6+	0.05	20	449.49	0.002	0.45	0	0.02	0.4	40	1.78
											WQI=93.47

Table 3: Results of the analysis of the physico-chemical parameters and calculation of the water quality index (WQI) for Sabon Gari [14].

S/N	Parameter	Standard (Sn)	1/Sn	Sum. 1/Sn	K = 1/sum.Sn	Wn = K/Sn	Ideal value	Vn = Mean conc.	Vn/Sn	Qn=Vn/Sn*10 ⁰	WnQn
1	PH	8.5	0.12	449.49	0.002	0.0002	7	6.64	0.78117647 1	78.11764706	0.02
2	Conductivity	1000	0.001	449.49	0.002	2.22	0	160	0.16	16.0	3.56
3	TDS	500	0.002	449.49	0.002	4.45	0	128	0.26	25.60	0.001
4	Salinity	500	0.002	449.49	0.002	4.45	0	88	0.18	17.60	7.83
5	Total chlorine	500	0.002	449.49	0.002	4.45	0	0.08	0.0001	0.016	7.12
6	Fluorine	0.05	20	449.49	0.002	0.045	0	0.005	0.1	10.00	0.45
7	Chloride	250	0.004	449.49	0.002	8.89	0	48.7	0.19	19.48	0.0001
8	Copper	1.3	0.77	449.49	0.002	0.001	0	0.01	0.007	0.77	0.001
9	Zinc	3	0.33	449.49	0.002	0.0007	0	0.02	0.0067	0.67	0.0004
10	Cadmium	0.005	200	449.49	0.002	0.45	0	0	0	0.00	0.00
11	Iron	2	0.5	449.49	0.002	0.001	0	0	0	0.00	0.00
12	Cr6+	0.05	20	449.49	0.002	0.04	0	0.025	0.5	50	2.22
										WQI =	2.69

The summary of the water quality index (WQI) calculations for each of the study areas is shown in Table 4 below

Table 4: The summary of the WQI calculations for each of the study[18].

S/N	Parameter	Unit	Investment Quarters	Sabon Gari
1	pH	-	7.70	6.64
2	Conductivity	($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	560	160
3	Total dissolved solids	(mg/L)	448	128
4	Salinity	(mg/L)	308	88
5	Total chlorine	(mg/L)	0.10	0.08
6	Fluoride	(mg/L)	0.53	0.005
7	Chloride	(mg/L)	170.80	48.70
8	Total Copper	(mg/L)	0.00	0.01
9	Total Zinc	(mg/L)	0.025	0.02
10	Total Cadmium	(mg/L)	0.005	0.00
11	Total Iron	(mg/L)	0.015	0.00
12	Hexavalent Chromium	(mg/L)	0.02	0.025
	WQI		93.47	2.69

Table 1 results will be used for the explanation of each parameter analyzed and compared with standard value of World Health Organization [17]. The results of the pH test show that the sample from Investment Quarters and Sabon Gari has a pH value of 7.7 and 6.64 respectively. This shows the pH values of the districts lie within the prescribed range of 6.50 to 8.50. Thus, the values obtained from the study areas shows the neutrality of the water, hence very good for consumption. The pH of a water sample is a measure of the acidity or alkalinity of the sample and the value ranges from 0 to 14 with pH value of 7 indicating neutrality. The pH values of less than 7.00 indicates acidity while values greater than 7.00 indicated alkalinity. The pH value of water influences some properties and attributes of the water such as solubility and availability of chemical constituents[18]. High pH levels are undesirable since they may impart a bitter taste to the water and the high degree of mineralization associated with alkaline water will result in the encrustation of water pipes and water-using appliances. Moreover, high pH levels also depress the effectiveness of disinfection by chlorination, thereby requiring the use of additional chlorine or longer contact times[19]. Electrical conductivity (EC) of water is an expression of the ability of water to conduct an electric current. This property is good measure of total salinity of the water sample and is a direct function of temperature. The result shows that the electrical conductivity values of the samples from Investment

Quarters and Sabon Gari are 560 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and 160 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, respectively. This shows that the EC values for all the study areas lie within the recommended limit of 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ by [20]. Total Dissolved Solid (TDS) is a parameter that measures the amount of dissolved solid substances in a water sample. They originate from dissolution or weathering of the rocks and soil, including dissolution of lime, gypsum and other slowly dissolved soil minerals [20]. Water with high dissolved solids generally are of inferior palatability and may induce an unfavourable physiological reaction in the transient consumer. In the current study, TDS of the samples from Investment Quarters was 448 mg/L and that of Sabon Gari was 128 mg/L. These values all lie within the prescribed limits of 500 mg/L by [21]. Groundwater salinity refers to the concentration of dissolved salts and minerals in underground water sources, such as aquifers and wells. The salinity can vary depending on the region and the geological layers through which the water has passed. In areas with high levels of salinity, such as coastal regions, it can be challenging to access freshwater for drinking and agricultural use [22]. The result shows that the salinity values of the samples from Investment Quarters and Sabon Gari are 308 mg/L and 88 mg/L, respectively. These values lie within the recommended limit of 500 mg/L by [22]. Groundwater total chlorine concentrations refers to the concentration of total chlorine in groundwater, which includes both free chlorine and

combined chlorine. The presence of chlorine in groundwater can result from natural processes, such as the oxidation of chloride ions, or from human activities such as the use of chlorine-containing disinfectants. In the current study, total chlorine of the sample from Investment Quarters is 0.1 mg/L and for Sabon Gari was obtained to be 0.08 mg/L. These values were all within the prescribed limits of 4 mg/L by [23]. Fluoride is a mineral occurring naturally in water in varying degree. From the result of the present research, Investment Quarters water sample showed the highest fluoride concentration value of 0.53 mg/L while that of Sabon Gari showed 0.005 mg/L. The result from Sabon Gari fall within the recommended standard of 0.05 mg/L by [24], while that of Investment Quarters exceed the recommended standard. A moderate quantity of fluoride ions in drinking water enhances good dental health and is effective in preventing tooth decay, particularly in children [25]. However, excess quantity of fluoride causes discolored teeth, a condition known as dental fluorosis [26]. Chloride occurs naturally in groundwater, streams, and lakes, but the presence of relatively high chloride concentration in freshwater (about 250 mg/L or more) may indicate wastewater pollution [27]. In the present study, the chloride concentration found from sample in Investment Quarters is 170.8 mg/L while that of Sabon gari is 48.7 mg/L which lie within the recommended value of 250 mg/L by [27]. High concentration of chloride is responsible for unpleasant salty taste in drinking water [28]. Copper is an essential substance to human life, but chronic exposure to contaminant drinking water with copper can result in the development of anemia, liver, and kidney damage [29]. In the present study, there was no copper present from the sample obtained from Investment Quarters whereas the sample from Sabon gari showed 0.01 mg/L, which both lie within the recommended value of 1.3 mg/L [30]. Lack of copper intake causes anemia, growth inhibition, and blood circulation problems [31]. Hence, water from Investment Quarters may result to such problems. Zinc is one of the major essential elements required by the human system [30]. Zinc plays several functions in the human body, such as wound healing, blood clotting, proper thyroid function, and maintenance of good vision [32]. From the result of the present research, Investment Quarters water sample showed total zinc concentration value of 0.025 mg/L while that of Sabon Gari showed 0.02 mg/L. Both values fall

within the recommended standard of 3.0 mg/L [33]. Cadmium is released to the environment in wastewater, and diffuse pollution is caused by contamination from fertilizers and local air pollution [34]. Contamination in drinking water may also be caused by impurities in the zinc of galvanized pipes and solders and some metal fittings. The result shows that the total cadmium concentration values of the sample from Investment Quarters is 0.005 mg/L while for Sabon Gari sample cadmium is not present. Both values lie within the recommended limit of 0.005 mg/L [35], but Investment Quarters result is at the maximum. This may result from the farming near the site and dumping of pollutant such as food waste, as food is the major daily source of exposure to cadmium. The kidney is the main target organ for cadmium toxicity [36]. Iron is generally associated with acidic ground water or anaerobic ground water. In the water, it can be associated with bitter/metallic taste, formation of sediment and yellow, red, and orange films, and discoloured clothing during washing [37]. The result shows that the total iron concentration values of the sample from Investment Quarters is 0.015 mg/L while for the sample from Sabon Gari iron is not present. Both results fall within the recommended standard of 2.0 mg/L [38]. Chromium is one of the toxic essential heavy metals. It is highly detrimental to humans when its concentration exceeds tolerable limits by humans. In the present study, the hexavalent chromium concentration found from the sample from Investment Quarters is 0.02 mg/L while that of Sabon gari is 0.025 mg/L. Both values lie within the recommended value of 0.05 mg/L by [39]. Within the required dose, chromium aids in catabolism of fat and carbohydrates, and the maintenance of blood glucose, especially in diabetic patients [40].

4.0 Conclusion

The importance of access to good quality water cannot be overemphasized. Increase in population coupled with the rise in human activity pose a great pressure on provision of safe drinking water. Effective water quality monitoring could assist in checking how daily activities affect the quality of water and impact of the introduction of pollutants on water quality. In evaluation of water quality index, a number of water quality parameters are transformed into a single number that indicates the quality of the water sample. This study has assessed the water quality based on WQI for selected

boreholes from Investment Quarters and Sabon Gari areas, in Jalingo Metropolis, it is concluded that the groundwater quality of the selected borehole in Sabon Gari is not harmful to human consumption, since all the physico-chemical parameters examined showed that all the parameters lie within the permissible limit prescribed by the World Health Organization. Whereas, the groundwater quality of the selected borehole in Investment Quarters is not safe for human consumption, this can be traced from the high levels of fluoride and cadmium observed from the WQI statistics, as fluoride exceeded the permissible limit while cadmium is at the maximum of the permissible limit prescribed by the World Health Organization.

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